

Analysis of Consumer Loyalty in the Household Laundry Industry in Padang City

Erni Febrina Harahap^{1*}, Rahul Guskar Hadi Wijaya²

^{1,2} Prodi Ekonomi Pembangunan, Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis, Universitas Bung Hatta

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 13 December 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Erni Febrina Harahap</p> <p>KEYWORDS: Service Quality, Location, Price, Trust, Digital Marketing, Consumer Loyalty</p>	<p>This study aims to analyze the influence of Service Quality, Location, Price, Trust, and Digital Marketing on Consumer Loyalty in the laundry industry in Padang City. The issue raised is the suboptimal customer loyalty amidst increasingly tight competition in the laundry business, so it is necessary to understand the factors that influence their loyalty. This study uses a quantitative approach with a multiple linear regression method. The research sample consisted of 67 consumers who use laundry services selected using a purposive random sampling technique, and the data were analyzed through t-tests, F-tests, and the coefficient of determination (R^2). The results of the study indicate that partially all independent variables have a positive and significant effect on consumer loyalty, with Trust as the most dominant variable. The simultaneous test produced a calculated F value of 248.873 with a significance of 0.000, which means that Service Quality, Location, Price, Trust, and Digital Marketing jointly influence loyalty. The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.953 indicates that 95.3% of the variation in consumer loyalty can be explained by the research model, while the remaining 4.7% is influenced by other factors outside the study. The conclusion of this study is that a combination of quality service, strategic location, appropriate prices, high consumer trust, and appropriate use of digital marketing can increase customer loyalty in the laundry industry.</p>

INTRODUCTION

The urban laundry service industry continues to show rapid growth, including in Padang City. Population growth, the growth of boarding houses, and increasingly dense community activities are driving demand for laundry services. According to data from the Padang City Cooperatives and MSMEs Office, the number of laundry businesses has increased significantly in the past ten years, from 121 units in 2015 to 219 units in 2024 (Table.1). This situation demonstrates significant market potential, but also creates intense competition among businesses. In addition to the increasing number of businesses, the distribution of laundry businesses in each district of Padang City also varies considerably. Data from 2025 shows that Kuranji District had the largest number of laundry businesses, with 43 units, followed by Nanggalo (42 units), and Koto Tengah (37 units). Conversely, the fewest laundry businesses were found in Lubuk Kilangan District (7 units), Padang Timur (8 units), and Bungus Teluk Kabung (8 units) at Table 2.

Table 1. Number of Laundry Businesses in Padang City 2015–2024

Year	Number
2015	121
2016	143
2017	147
2018	155
2019	164
2020	181
2021	192
2022	198
2023	204
2024	219

Source: Padang City Cooperatives & MSMEs Service Database, 2025

This situation indicates that laundry businesses have significant potential, but also face the challenge of intense competition. In such condition, customer loyalty is a crucial

factor in determining business sustainability. Customer loyalty is defined as a customer's tendency to continue using a particular service even when many alternatives are available. Griffin (2015) explains that loyal customers not only make repeat purchases but also recommend the service to others. This demonstrates that loyalty plays a strategic role in driving business growth, as the cost of retaining existing customers is typically lower than acquiring new ones.

Table 2. Distribution of Laundry Businesses in Padang City in 2025

Subdistrict	Amount
Padang Selatan	16
Padang Timur	8
Padang Utara	21
Padang Barat	10
Lubuk Begalung	16
lubuk Kilangan	7
Pauh	11
Bungus Teluk Kabung	8
Kuranji	43
Nanggalo	42
Koto Tangah	37
Total	219

Source: Padang City Cooperative and MSME Office Database 2025

The factors influencing consumer loyalty are diverse. Service quality is a key factor. Fast, friendly, and consistent service will increase satisfaction and strengthen consumer engagement with the service provider (Lovelock & Wirtz, 2011). Business location also plays a crucial role, as ease of access, environmental safety, and proximity to customers are key considerations for consumers when choosing a laundry service (Kotler et al., 2018). Furthermore, pricing that aligns with service quality can foster positive value perceptions, encouraging consumer loyalty. In line with this, Efdison et al. (2023) emphasized that price is a crucial factor influencing consumer decisions. If the price is perceived as commensurate with the benefits received, consumer loyalty will be strengthened. In addition to service, location, and price, trust also plays a significant role in building loyalty. Consumers who are confident in the quality and integrity of a service are more likely to continue using it even when there are many alternatives (Kim et al., 2008). Trust can be built through consistent service, transparency of information, and guaranteed security for entrusted items. Technological advancements have also provided a new dimension in building loyalty. Digital marketing, through social media and online platforms, allows service providers to interact more intensively with consumers, provide information quickly, and build brand image. According to Kotler & Keller (2021), digital marketing strategies can strengthen long-term relationships between businesses and

customers by opening up broader and more personal communication channels. Several previous studies have highlighted the influence of these variables on consumer loyalty, but research specifically on laundry businesses in Padang City is relatively limited. Therefore, this study was conducted to analyze the influence of service quality, location, price, trust, and digital marketing on consumer loyalty in laundry businesses in Padang City. The results are expected to provide both theoretical and practical contributions for businesses in increasing competitiveness and retaining customers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer Loyalty

Consumer loyalty is a customer's commitment to continue using a particular product or service despite numerous other options available. It also reflects the ongoing emotional connection between you and your customers, reflected in their willingness to interact with you and repeatedly purchase from you compared to your competitors. Loyalty is a byproduct of positive customer experiences with you and serves to build trust (Putri, 2024).

Service Quality

Service quality is one of the main determinants of customer loyalty. Good service encompasses aspects of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles (Lovelock & Wirtz, 2011). Customers who perceive prompt, friendly, and consistent service will develop a stronger emotional attachment to the service provider. This is consistent with research conducted by Fida et al. (2020), Octarinie (2018), Bramantyo et al. (2022), Rahayu & Nurlaela Wati (2018), and Wijaya Surya Mega Petra & Lomi Risela (2019), which found that service quality has a positive and significant influence on customer loyalty.

Location

Business location is a crucial factor in attracting customers, particularly in the service sector. Easily accessible, safe, and close to customers increases the likelihood of repeat purchases (Kotler & Keller, 2018). According to Putri et al. (2021), businesses strategically located, such as near campuses or residential areas, tend to have a higher customer base. This finding is supported by previous research by Putri et al. (2021), which found that location has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty.

Price

Price is one of the marketing mix elements that most influences purchasing decisions. According to Kotler & Keller (2019), price is the amount of money consumers exchange for the benefits of a product or service. According to Efdison et al. (2023), price plays a crucial role in the sales process because it is a form of incentive from the company. This aligns with the findings of Hidayat & Widodo (2022),

who stated that price has a positive and significant effect on consumer loyalty.

Trust

Trust is a consumer's belief that a service provider is capable of delivering services according to expectations. Kim et al. (2008) state that trust is built through positive experiences, transparency, and service integrity. Companies that maintain consistent service and guarantee the safety of consumer goods will be more trusted. This is supported by the findings of Arya Daffa Wibisono & Lukman Cahyadi (2024), who stated that trust has a positive and significant effect on consumer loyalty.

Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is a marketing strategy that utilizes digital technologies such as social media, websites, and applications. According to Kotler & Keller (2021), digital marketing enables more intense interactions with consumers and builds long-term relationships. Research by Putri et al. (2021) shows that digital marketing can increase customer engagement and strengthen loyalty. The use of social media, digital loyalty programs, and active online communication have been shown to increase the likelihood of consumers retaining a service. In research conducted by Sidi et al. (2019), it was found that digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on consumer loyalty.

METHODS

The design of this study is to determine the influence of service quality, location, price, trust and digital marketing on consumer loyalty in the household laundry industry in Padang City that using multiple linear regression analysis. The independent variables in this study are service quality (X1), location (X2), price (X3), trust (X4), and digital marketing (X5). Meanwhile, the dependent variable in this study is consumer loyalty (Y). A population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn (Sugiyono, 2017). The population of this study includes consumers, namely all consumers who use laundry services in the city of Padang, whose number is unknown. The sample selection method in this study was probability random sampling, a random sampling method. With this method, the entire population is assumed to have an equal chance of being included in the research sample. According to Sugiyono (2011), if the population is large and the researcher cannot study everything in the population, for example due to limited funds, manpower, and time, then the researcher can use a sample drawn from that population. The sample in this study was representative of laundry service users in Padang City. Because the population size is unknown, the sample size is calculated using the Cochran formula (Sugiyono 2017). The confidence level used is 90%, with a Z value of 1.64 and a

maximum error rate of 10%. The sample size in this study is as follows:

$$n = \frac{(1,64)^2 \times 0,5 \times 0,5}{(0,10)^2} = \frac{2,6896 \times 0,25}{0,01} = \frac{0,6724}{0,01} = 67,24$$

Based on the sample calculation, the required sample size was 67.24 respondents, which rounded up to 67 respondents. Validation testing is the accuracy of the collected data with the actual data on the object being studied (Sugiyono, 2017). The testing technique used is correlation through the product-moment correlation coefficient with a minimum R table of 0.2369, and for reliability, the alpha coefficient is greater than 0.60 (Priyatno, 2013). The ordinal score of each question item being tested for validity is correlated with the overall ordinal score of the item. If the R-count value is greater than the R-table value (R-count > R-table), the question item is declared valid. If the R-count value is less than the R-table value (R-count < R-table), the question item is declared invalid and will be removed from the questionnaire or replaced with a revised statement. Validity and reliability measurements were carried out on all adopted question items, where consumer loyalty (Y) has 8 question items (Kotler & Keller, 2016; Oliver, 2014), service quality (X1) has 10 question items (Zeithaml et al., 2017; Ladhari, 2016), location (X2) has 9 question items (Tjiptono, 2019), (Kotler Philip & Keller, 2016), price (X3) has 8 question items (Tjiptono, 2020; Zeithaml et al., 2018), trust (X4) has 7 question items (Morgan & Hunt, 2014; Kotler & Keller, 2016), and digital marketing (X5) has 8 question items (Chaffey & Ellis, 2019; Damian & Calvin, 2016). Data processing with multiple linear regression tests were carried out with SPSS.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) Validity, Reliability, and Classical Assumption Tests

Results The validity test results show that all statement items in the variables of service quality, location, price, trust, and digital marketing have a calculated r value greater than the r table (0.235), so that all indicators are declared valid. Furthermore, the results of the reliability test show that the Cronbach's Alpha value for each variable is above 0.70, namely 0.969 for service quality, 0.884 for location, 0.861 for price, 0.862 for trust, and 0.758 for digital marketing. This proves that the research instrument has good internal consistency (Table.3).

Classical assumption testing also supports the model's feasibility. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test yielded an Asymp. Sig. value of 0.200, which is greater than 0.05, indicating a normal distribution of the data. The multicollinearity test showed that all independent variables had tolerance values above 0.10 and VIFs below 10, indicating the absence of multicollinearity. Meanwhile, the heteroscedasticity test showed that all variables had significance values greater than 0.05, indicating that the model was free from heteroscedasticity symptoms. Therefore, validity, reliability, and classical assumption tests, the

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research instrument is declared suitable for use, and the data obtained meets the requirements for multiple linear regression analysis.

Table 3. Validity, Reliability, and Classical Assumption Tests

variabel	item	r hitung	Cronbach's Alpha	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	Multikolinieritas		Heteroskedasitas
					Tolerance	VIF	Sig.
Service Quality	X1.1	0,872	0,969	0,200	0,220	4,554	0,988
	X1.2	0,902					
	X1.3	0,883					
	X1.4	0,869					
	X1.5	0,862					
	X1.6	0,889					
	X1.7	0,903					
	X1.8	0,878					
	X1.9	0,897					
	X1.10	0,991					
Location	X2.1	0,694	0,884	0,200	0,279	3,590	0,547
	X2.2	0,686					
	X2.3	0,534					
	X2.4	0,708					
	X2.5	0,700					
	X2.6	0,740					
	X2.7	0,799					
	X2.8	0,759					
	X2.9	0,841					
Price	X3.1	0,627	0,861	0,200	0,828	1,208	0,946
	X3.2	0,734					
	X3.3	0,733					
	X3.4	0,735					
	X3.5	0,801					
	X3.6	0,668					
	X3.7	0,749					
	X3.8	0,651					
Trust	X4.1	0,711	0,862	0,200	0,278	3,600	0,498
	X4.2	0,74					
	X4.3	0,743					
	X4.4	0,766					
	X4.5	0,763					
	X4.6	0,712					
	X4.7	0,759					
Digital Marketing	X5.1	0,633	0,758	0,200	0,540	1,851	0,331
	X5.2	0,685					
	X5.3	0,645					
	X5.4	0,645					
	X5.5	0,703					
	X5.6	0,584					

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	X5.7	0,584				
	X5.8	0,469				

The t-test results show that all independent variables have a positive and significant effect on consumer loyalty. Service quality has a t-value of 3.354 with a significance level of 0.001, meaning that the better the service, the higher the customer loyalty. These results are also consistent with

previous studies that state that service quality has a positive and significant effect on consumer loyalty, as stated by Fida et al., (2020), Octarinie (2018), Bramantyo et al., (2022), Rahayu & Nurlaela Wati (2018), and Wijaya Surya Mega Petra & Lomi Risela (2019).

2). t-Test

Table 4. t-Test

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2.184	1.076		-2.029	.047
	Service Quality	.142	.042	.198	3.354	.001
	Location	.323	.047	.360	6.871	.000
	Price	.091	.030	.092	3.015	.004
	Trust	.412	.055	.392	7.463	.000
	Digital Marketing	.093	.046	.076	2.012	.049

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Loyalty

Location showed a significant effect with a t-value of 6.871 and a significance level of 0.000, indicating that a strategic location increases the frequency of service use. This research is further supported by the results of research by Luthina Nofindri et al. (2021) and Putri et al. (2021), which showed that business location has a positive and significant effect on consumer loyalty in using certain services. Price also had a positive effect, with a t-value of 3.015 and a significance level of 0.004, indicating that appropriate pricing can retain customers and increase consumer loyalty to the company. These results are consistent with research by Kaura et al. (2015) and Hidayat & Widodo (2022), which found that price significantly impacts loyalty and revenue for both service and product businesses.

Trust had the strongest influence, with a t-value of 7.463 and a significance level of 0.000, indicating that the higher the consumer's trust, the more loyal they are to laundry services. This research aligns with findings from Nugroho et al. (2022) and Arya Daffa Wibisono & Lukman Cahyadi (2024), which state that trust significantly drives consumer loyalty in the service business. Meanwhile, digital marketing also had a significant impact, with a t-value of 2.012 and a significance level of 0.049, indicating that the use of digital media supports increased consumer loyalty. This research supports studies by Sidi et al. (2019) and Putri et al. (2021), which concluded that digital marketing has a positive and significant impact on consumer loyalty in the service industry.

3). F-Test

Table 5. F-Test (Simultan)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4206.765	5	841.353	248.873	.000 ^b
	Residual	206.220	61	3.381		
	Total	4412.985	66			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Loyalty

b. Predictors: (Constant), Digital Marketing, Price, Trust, Location, Service Quality

The F test results show that simultaneously Service Quality, Location, Price, Trust, and Digital Marketing have a significant effect on Consumer Loyalty with a calculated F

value of 248.873 and a significance of 0.000 <0.05. This proves that the five variables together are able to explain variations in changes in customer loyalty in laundry

businesses. This finding supports the service marketing theory which states that consumer loyalty is formed from a combination of excellent service, easily accessible locations,

appropriate prices, built trust, and effective digital marketing strategies, so that collectively increase consumers' desire to continue using the same service.

4). Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Table 6. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.976 ^a	.953	.949	1.839

a. Predictors: (Constant), Digital Marketing, Price, Trust, Location, Service Quality

The coefficient of determination test results showed an R² value of 0.953, meaning that 95.3% of the contribution of the increase and decrease in consumer loyalty to laundry businesses in Padang City can be explained by service quality, location, price, trust, and digital marketing. Meanwhile, the remaining 4.7% is explained by other factors not examined in this study, such as offline promotions, communication quality, or other external factors. The high R² value indicates that the regression model used has excellent predictive ability in describing consumer loyalty to household laundry industry in Padang City.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study concludes that Service Quality, Location, Price, Trust, and Digital Marketing have a positive and significant effect on Consumer Loyalty in household laundry industry in Padang City, both partially and simultaneously. The t-test results show that each variable has a significant effect, with Trust being the most dominant factor in increasing loyalty. The F-test indicates that the five variables together make a significant contribution to changes in consumer loyalty. The coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.953 indicates that 95.3% of the variation in loyalty can be explained by the model used, while the remaining 4.7% is influenced by other factors not examined. These findings confirm that the combination of quality service, strategic location, appropriate price, high consumer trust, and appropriate use of digital marketing can shape long-term customer loyalty.

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